

THE SCIENTIFIC BASIS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT AND
IMPLEMENTATION OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES FOR
VOCATIONAL TRAINING OF STUDENTS IN THE EDUCATIONAL
AND EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Annotation: *This article presents reflections on improving the professional orientation of students in general secondary schools.*

Keywords: *profession, reader own interest, ability, knowledge, practice.*

In the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated may 11, 2022 PQ-241 “on additional measures for the development of folk education”, starting from the 2022-2023 academic year, the organization of various meetings and sightseeing classes for students in Grades 5-7 with the aim of familiarizing them with the work activities of the professional At the same time, it was determined to establish priority professions for schoolchildren in accordance with socio-economic potential and growth points, and to take measures to educate students in Grades 10 and 11 in these professions, including vocational training centers, vocational training centers for residents of the neighborhood in educational institutions where short-term courses are opened.

Analysis of the structure of information support for the work of vocational training of streamers was carried out;

on the basis of the educational program of general secondary education of students, a classification of professions that they can get acquainted with in the course of the lesson was determined;

in schools, information on the classification of professions required according to local-territorial conditions and each of them was collected and systematized, which was not directly looked at in the course of the lesson;

in extracurricular activities, the classification developed in the organization of vocational training acts as the basis, ensuring the effectiveness of vocational training work for students on the basis of local requirements.

Form 1.1. Structure of the organization of practical experimental training

The school administration and the pedagogical team are faced with the task of ensuring that each student has the opportunity to choose one of the faculties, which later becomes mandatory for him. Elective classes are held

on the basis of a special program that serves to increase the independence and activity of students, to develop their mental abilities. In the organization of such educational activities, mainly practical-experimental classes of extracurricular activities and forms of excursions were used (1.2. form).

1.2.- form. Directions and structural structure of excursions

When organizing excursions, which are considered one of the forms of extracurricular activities, we drew attention to their class-lesson system, as well as the following aspects that are fundamentally different from practical ones:

a) Although all of the excursions to be conducted are guided by the teacher, he may not be well acquainted with all the objects of the excursion, in such cases the responsible representative of the enterprise, institution or farm where the excursion is being organized conducts the training;

b) the duration of the excursion varies, and when organizing them, regional, seasonal and excursion are based on the characteristics of the organized object. In particular, the organization of an excursion to an agricultural enterprise during the period of harvesting, during the conduct of technical care for motor vehicles, allows you to achieve the highest productivity;

c) the guidance method of the excursion, represented by the teacher or the object on which the excursion is organized, and the activities of the students may differ.

During the excursion, moving from one place to another. Therefore, students are required to strictly follow the discipline. Teachers in the process of observing the object periodically ask questions, write down the necessary information. At the end of the excursion, the teacher conducts a conversation, linking what he observed today to previously mastered materials. It is possible to write a statement or essay based on the materials of the excursion.

Discussion, round table, practical conference, seminar, etc., organized as an unconventional form of education, are organized on important topics of a particular subject and serve to form in students the ability to think independently, promote one's own opinion, substantiate and protect it. In the organization of such classes, the accuracy of the goal, as well as the active participation of teachers, plays an important role.

Classes held in the form of an exhibition and a miracle field have a competitive nature and encourage students to engage.

The success of training in vocational guidance depends not only on its form, but also on the effectiveness of the techniques used. Teaching methods represent methods for achieving the goals set by them in teaching, as well as ways of theoretical practical orientation of educational material.

The process of professional orientation in a person is carried out through special scientific and practical activities. At the stages of the formation of the student as a person, the individual and society are considered as a single system, the requirements for the relations of the market economy of the transition period are taken into account. In conclusion, the fact that the content of vocational guidance of students is chosen based on many factors, such as the prospect of the level of socio-economic, cultural development of

our republic, the needs of society, the goals of rational use of technical and technological processes, is a fact for which proof is not required.

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